

Oxine *N*-Oxide as an Analytical Reagent for the Colorimetric Estimation of Cerium (IV) and its Comparison with Oxine as a Chelating Agent

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Oxine *N*-oxide has been investigated as an analytical reagent for the colorimetric estimation of cerium (IV), which produces a deep brownish red, water-soluble complex with an ethanolic solution of the reagent. The complex is quite stable and the intensity of the colour remains unchanged between pH 2.0 and 6.5. The complex obeys Lambert-Beer's law at 420 m μ up to a dilution of 9 p.p.m. of cerium. The trivalent rare earths cerium, lanthanum and yttrium do not interfere in the above estimation.

Very little is known about the formation of co-ordination compounds with heterocyclic *N*-oxides ((Katritzky, *Quart. Rev.*, 1956, 10, 395). *N*-Oxides form stable salts with strong acids unless other negative groups are present. The basicity is, however, considerably less than that of the corresponding parent compound; the *pK* values of the conjugate acids of (e.g.) pyridine and pyridine *N*-oxide are respectively 5.29 and 0.79 (Jaffe and Doak, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 4441). We carried out the study of oxine *N*-oxide as an analytical reagent and investigated in detail its uranium (VI) and iron (III) complexes spectrophotometrically (Bhat and Jain, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, 19 B, 16, 295). The *pK* value of oxine *N*-oxide has now been determined by pH titrations in 50% (v/v) dioxane—water mixture and it is found to be 4.6 as compared to 10.8 for oxine (Irving and Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2910). The basicity of oxine *N*-oxide is thus considerably decreased by the introduction of the N⁺—O⁻ in the heterocyclic molecule, with the result that the metal chelates of oxine *N*-oxide become less stable than those of oxine (Bhat *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

During our spectrophotometric studies of uranium (VI)-oxine *N*-oxide complex, it was observed that cerium (IV) ions seriously interfered in the estimation of uranium and this led us to study the reaction of cerium(IV) with oxine *N*-oxide. We have found that this reagent has certain advantages over oxine for the colorimetric determination of cerium(IV).

Although several organic reagents have been developed for their colorimetric reactions with cerium(IV), few have been adapted to quantitative colorimetric determination (Snell and Snell, "Colorimetric Methods of Analysis", Vol II, 1954, p. 607). Since tetravalent cerium ion is yellow, that furnishes one direct means of determination. Some of the organic reagents recommended for colorimetric determination of cerium are brucine (Shemyakin and Volkova, *J. Gen. Chem.*, 1939, 9, 698), pyrogallol (Shemyakin *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1935, 5, 667), and gallic acid (Shemyakin, *Zavodskaya Lab.*, 1934, 3, 1090). These reagents suffer from various disadvantages. For instance, brucine lacks sensitivity and the intensity of the colour produced increases with time. In the case of pyrogallol, the colour formed varies from a violet sol to a dark purple-red precipitate, depending on the concentration of the reagents. Both pyrogallol and gallic acid can be used only at high pH. Tiron (Sarma, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 538), which gives water-soluble complex, has also been used. Westwood and Mayer (*Analyst*, 1948, 73, 275) used oxine for the extraction in chloroform of cerous ions from aqueous solutions having pH 9.9-10.5.

When an ethanolic solution of oxine *N*-oxide is treated with an aqueous solution of cerium (IV) salt, a deep brownish red, water-soluble complex is instantaneously produced. The complex is quite stable and the colour remains unchanged between *pH* 2.0 and 6.5. The complex obeys Lambert-Beer's law to a dilution of 9.0 p.p.m. of cerium and the optical density remains unaffected between 10° and 30°. The reagent has an additional advantage, namely, no special organic solvent is needed for extraction of the complex since it is water-soluble. The trivalent rare earths cerium, lanthanum, and yttrium do not interfere.

EXPERIMENTAL

Oxine *N*-oxide was prepared by the method previously described (Bhat *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Standard cerium (IV) solutions were prepared with cerium (IV) ammonium nitrate (B.D.H., A.R.). All other reagents were either of A.R. or *pro analysi* quality.

The absorption spectra studies of cerium (IV)-oxine *N*-oxide complex were made with a Unicam spectrophotometer SP 600. All other absorption measurements were made using a Lumetron photoelectric colorimeter. A Beckman *pH* meter, Model H 2, was used for *pH* measurements.

FIG. 1. Absorption spectrum of cerium (IV)-oxine *N*-oxide complex.

Absorption Spectra.—The ultraviolet absorption spectrum of oxine *N*-oxide has already been reported (*loc. cit.*). The cerium (IV)-oxine *N*-oxide complex did not have any maximum absorption band in the visible region of the spectrum. The nature of the absorption curve (Fig. 1) shows that the absorption maximum must be in the ultraviolet region. The wave length filter 420 $m\mu$ was chosen for the subsequent colorimetric studies of the complex. At this wave length, the absorption due to the reagent was negligible.

Minimum Amount of Oxine *N*-oxide necessary for the Estimation of Cerium (IV).—The optical densities at 420 $m\mu$ of a series of solutions containing oxine *N*-oxide and cerium (IV) in the molar ratio of 0.5:1 to 9:1 were determined. The results plotted in Fig. 2 show that the portion of the curve up to A is almost a straight line up to the molar ratio of 5.0. For the estimation of cerium (IV), however, the molar ratio of oxine *N*-oxide to cerium (IV) was maintained at 10 in the subsequent studies.

Effect of *pH* on Cerium-oxine *N*-oxide Complex.—The stock solution of the complex was 1.0×10^{-3} *M* with respect to cerium. An aliquot (10 c.c.) of this solution was taken in a 25 c.c. measuring flask and the volume made to 25 c.c. using dilute solutions of HCl and

NaOH for pH adjustments. The complex showed a minimum and unchanged transmission between a wide pH range of 2.0 and 6.5 (Table I). The solution developed slight turbidity above pH 6.5. The pH of each of the solutions was determined using a suitable glass electrode.

Molar ratio of oxine N-oxide to cerium (IV) salt.
 FIG. 2. Variation in the optical density of the complex solution with change in molar ratio of oxine N-oxide and Ce (IV).

TABLE I

No.	pH.	%Transmission.	No.	pH.	%Transmission.
1.	1.0	77.0	5.	3.3	66.0
2.	1.5	73.0	6.	4.4	65.5
3.	2.0	66.3	7.	6.0	65.5
4.	2.5	66.0	8.	6.5	65.5

Stability of the Colour of the Complex.—The colour of the cerium (IV)-oxine N-oxide complex was found to be quite stable and no change in the transmission percentage could be observed even after one week. The absorption by the complex remains unaffected between 10° and 30°.

Lambert-Beer's Law.—Varying known volumes of a stock solution of the ceric complex (strength 1.0×10^{-3} M with respect to ceric ions) were taken in a 25 c.c. measuring flask and the volume was made to 25 c.c. using distilled water. Transmission percentage in each case was found with the colorimeter using filter 420 m μ (Table II).

TABLE II

No.	Conc. of Ce(IV) ions (moles per litre).	%Transmission.
1.	0.06×10^{-3}	98.0
2.	0.10×10^{-3}	86.0
3.	0.20×10^{-3}	78.5
4.	0.40×10^{-3}	67.5
5.	0.60×10^{-3}	54.0
6.	0.80×10^{-3}	42.0
7.	1.00×10^{-3}	32.0

When the above concentrations of cerium (IV) ions are plotted against the transmission percentage, a straight line is obtained; this shows that Lambert-Beer's law is obeyed by the coloured complex up to a dilution of 9 p.p.m. of cerium in the solution.

Interference due to Foreign Ions.—The stock solution of the complex was $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ with respect to cerium, having 10 as the mole ratio of the reagent to the metal ion. Known volumes of this solution were taken in a 25 c.c. measuring flask and mixed with a known amount of a solution of the foreign salt; the volume was made to 25 c.c. with water. The transmission percentage of this solution was determined within five minutes of mixing. The concentration of the foreign salt was progressively increased till the transmission changed by 2% of the theoretical values. It was found that a solution containing 0.087 mg. of ceric ion could be estimated for the metal in presence of 0.6 mg./c.c. of cerium (III); the solution containing 0.029 mg. of ceric ion could be estimated in presence of 0.674 mg./c.c. of lanthanum (III) and 0.72 mg./c.c. of yttrium (III). Uranium, thorium, and fluoride ions, however, interfere in the above estimation and therefore their separation by usual methods is necessary before estimation of cerium (IV) with this reagent.

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